

The Mediating Role of Information Technology (IT) on the relationship between Supply Chain Management and Firms' Performance: Evidence from Rwanda

Author's Details: Katlego Tumo Wantlo

Affiliation: School of Management, Jiangsu University, No 301 Xuefu Road, 212013, Zhenjiang, Jiangsu Province, P. R. China

Email Address:katlegowantlo2@gmail.com

Abstract

This study's major objective is to evaluate the mediating role of IT on the relationship between supply chain management and firm performance in Rwanda. The research design used simple random and stratified sampling methods as a representative sample of SMEs in Rwanda. The sample size of the study was 300 respondents. In pursuit of data collection for the study, both supplier and buyer relationships were incorporated. However, the participants were logistics managers, procurement or purchasing officers/managers, or supply chain managers who considered the field interviews' appropriate participants. The data was analyzed using appropriate models for appropriateness, convenience, clarity, and simplicity. The models such as structural equation modelling was used to evaluate the direct and indirect effect of IT on supply chain management in Rwanda. However, the elliptical reweighted least squares (ERLS) procedure of the EQS program was used as the statistical tools to analyze the research. The overall fit statistics show that the model suits the results very well in its entirety ($\chi^2 = 1076.96$ with $df = 249$, $CFI = 0.917$, $RMSEA = 0.062$, $NFI = 0.913$, $NNFI = 0.956$). However, IT advancement has a substantial positive impact on both IT alignment ($t = 0.321$, $p < 0.05$) and supply chain management ($t = 0.612$, $p < 0.05$) in the hypothesized relationship. Thus, hypothesis 2 is supported in this findings which implies that information technology infrastructure positively relates to supply chain management as it is evidential that both IT alignment and advancement showed positive and significant relationship with supply chain management. The total effect was assessed considering supply chain management with the mediating effect of IT alignment ($t = 0.321$, $p < 0.05$), and IT advancement ($t = 0.612$, $p < 0.05$) as well as firm performance ($t = 0.512$, $p < 0.05$) indicating that H1 and H3 are supported which implies that supply chain management positively relates to IT infrastructure which positively influence firms' performance significantly. To attract and retain customers, businesses must be committed to consistently providing high-quality services at a low or managed rate. This can be accomplished by instilling a customer service philosophy in the supply chain management department. In today's world, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is rapidly evolving. In light of the findings, it was observed that information technology plays crucial role in supply chain management such that it eliminates paper works and smoothen workflow.

Keywords: Supply chain management; Information technology; Firm performance; Marketing performance; Firm size

1. Introduction

According to Min et al. (2019), Supply chains and manufacturing logistics systems are an integral portion of the everyday initiatives of many technical and personal activities in contemporary life, and they are highly relevant for global growth. The rapid changes in the diverse markets as well as the nature of the physical, financial, social and technological developments have led to the evolution of supply chain management (Garay-Rondero et al., 2019). Supply chain management is stationary, but its scale, shape, configuration and way of organizing, controlling and managing constantly evolve (MacCarthy et al., 2016). Supply chain management (SCM) has been described as a progressively significant area of leadership to help companies optimize supply chain activities (Markus, 2000). Sharma and Kaur (2017) have described supply chain management as all those activities involving the movement of products from a starting point to the final consumer. This is achieved primarily by maintaining tight control over company vendors' internal stock, internal distribution, sales and stock. In a system comprising of suppliers, producers, customers, and distributors; supply chain management includes the flows of content, knowledge, and finance (Niu, 2010). There has been a transition in business relationships from conventional market-based relationships to more cooperative relationships such as strategic partnership-like relationships in the past decade (Bensaou, 1997; Scott, 2000). Academic and realistic literature have both recognized that market competitions are no longer

between distinct businesses, but somewhat between supply chains in a variety of industries (Oh & Rhee, 2008; Lambert & Cooper, 2000; Straub et al., 2004). The emergence of a knowledge-intensive economy is one of the key explanations for the paradigm change in supply chain (SC) relationships (Niu, 2010).

In a knowledge-intensive economy, the worth of most goods and services relies primarily on the creation of knowledge-based intangibles, such as technical know-how, marketing, product design, client preferences, and getting knowledge on value-added networks. As the production of novel products turn into more multifaceted and business conditions become extra diverse and competitive, it is probable that the expertise and information required to provide worth to end consumers is no longer limited to a sole company (Inkpen & Dinur, 1998; Hult et al., 2004; Lincoln et al., 1998).

In today's competitive marketplace, it appears a lot of firms are struggling to survive. Conventional supply chain management would not assist a company in meeting business and consumer demands. The advancement of technology has changed the face of the supply chain as it was previously known. Information technology aids in the creation of a smart and reliable supply chain system. The challenge has to do with the creation of economic value via through vibrant organizations, with relevant knowledge in the applications and innovations of strategic tools (Jadhav, 2015). Information technology plays a critical role in improving the efficiency and performance of the supply chain drivers. The use of inter organizational systems for information sharing and/or retrieval across organizational boundaries is referred to as information technology. For any company, there is a growing need for fully integrated supply chain management solutions that include all network strategy functionality, supply chain configuration, transportation, demand forecasting, and warehouse management systems (Jadhav, 2015). For production logistics and SC applications, information and communication technologies (ICT) and the Internet of Things (IoT)-based cyber-physical system (CPS) architecture have led to the implementation and acceleration of innovations needed for industry digitization (Tu et al., 2018). For any organization, information technology is very crucial for the smooth implementation of effective and efficient supply chain management. IT makes the supply chain transparent to management, which is useful for enhancing business efficiency. The crucial role IT plays in SSM is reducing the process of transactions between supply chain partners through cost effective data (Sharma & Kaur, 2017).

Supply chain management is becoming a more useful management method for companies looking to improve their operations. Despite the widespread use of information and communication technology in supply chains, there is a lack of systematic evidence to show how IT enables companies to create value in the supply chain system. In addition, as supply chain priorities move beyond operational competence to meet higher-order objectives, such as considering the complexities of the market and seeking new collaboration strategies to provide greater consumer worth, the abilities required for supply chains to retain their competitive advantages need to be well understood by both researchers and practitioners. Secondly, considering the value of information technology for efficient supply chain management, observed research evaluating how information technology is in practice used for the purposes of supply chain management is narrow. More precisely, previous work on information technology and supply chain management has focused either on modelling the advantages of interorganizational information technology and information sharing, or on evaluating the effect of specific technologies on supply chain performance. Consequently, the practical use of IT in the management of the supply chain and the reasons for the particular use of information technology remain uncertain (Auramo et al., 2005).

Given the above assertions, this present study tend to investigate the relationship between supply chain management and firms' performance emphasizing on the mediating role of information technology. This research is intended to contribute to both research and practice to some extent. On the theoretical hand, this research will help to build a theoretical construct for the role of information technology in supply chain management practices and their economic effects on firms in emerging economies. The study consists of five parts: (1) introduction; (2) literature review; (3) research methodology; (4) findings and discussions and (5) conclusion.

2. Theoretical background and Literature review

2.1 Theoretical background and conceptual framework

According to the resource-based view, sources of competitive advantage operate under the assumption that firm resources are immobile and heterogeneous (Barney, 1991). Disparities in market performance are primarily due to valuable, exclusive, non-substitutable, and inimitable skills and resources (Wernerfelt, 1984; Barney, 1991). Moreover, a company's competitive advantage would be preserved if it employs a technique that is difficult to duplicate by competitors (Barney, 1991). Marketing scholars who connect different kinds of market-based assets (Srivastava et al., 1998; 1999) and competencies (Day, 1994) with a firm's ultimate business performance have concentrated on how to exploit capital in establishing and sustaining competitive advantage (Hunt & Morgan, 1995; Srivastava et al., 2001).

Information technology as part of a firm's resource portfolio cannot satisfy the resource-based view requirement while operating alone. IT-based advantages tend to disappear rapidly due to low barriers to replication and acquisition by other firms (Clemons & Row, 1991). As a result, one of the most important research topics in recent years has been how IT can provide a company with a long-term competitive advantage. Powell and Dent-Micallef (1997), for instance, found that as information technology is incorporated into an organization by resource co-specialization and interdependence, its value grows. In this study, it looks into how information technology is being used in the supply chain communication system (SCCS). It argues that incorporating information technology into a firm's supply chain structure will help it demonstrate greater organizational skills, such as supply chain management competencies, which are firm-explicit and difficult to replicate across establishments. The information advantage gained through the use of advanced technology, as well as the complementary advantages gained through the use of an integrated structure, provide a firm with sources of long-term competitive advantage (Bharadwaj, 2000).

Figure 1 Conceptual framework

2.2 Literature review

2.2.1 Supply chain management and firm performance

The success of a business is not solely based on its own performance; rather, the performance of all supply chain partners adds to the business's overall performance. According to Gharakhani et al. (2012), De Toni and Nassimbeni (2000), Narasimhan and Kim (2002), and Li et al. (2005), supply chain management is a component in the system that emphasizes on the interaction between providers and the business. However, it guarantees that upstream logistics systems are functioning properly. It begins by choosing the right suppliers, who are able to manufacture and distribute according to the firm's specifications, on time, so that the business can obtain a consistent and faultless supply of products to meet the needs of the customers (Day and Lichtenstein, 2006). Supply chain management has an influence on the amount of market processes, including sourcing executive and planning, supplier performance management, sourcing analytics, supplier cooperation (Boddy et al., 2000), collaborative problem solving and planning (Gunasekaran & Chung, 2004; Gandhi et al., 2017), and all platforms that enables a company to maximize sourcing. Supply chain relationship management that is successful allows a business to get a competitive advantage, particularly throughout challenging times (Gandhi et al., 2017; Raut et al., 2012). According to Castelli & Brun (2010), collaboration between manufacturers and retailers creates value to end users. As a result, effective supply chain relationship management ensures a continuous flow of information and resources between the supplier and the business, as well as the availability of the right product at the right time, thus enhancing the firm's productivity (Sundram et al., 2011; Gandhi et al., 2017).

H1: There is a positive effect of supply chain management on firm performance

2.2.2 Information technology infrastructure and supply chain management

In this study, information technology alignment refers to how closely a company's information technology matches that of its channel partners. The degree to which information technology is integrated in the supply chain is referred to as information technology integration, and it necessitates channel participants organizing and aligning their business practices in order to achieve productivity (Powell, 1992). Supply chain communication system's functional adequacy is dependent on the development and alignment of information technology (Hausman & Stock, 2003). Information technology alignment between partners, on the other hand, is hard to achieve (Clemons & Row, 1993), and it necessitates a dedication of resources and communication across the channel relationship. In reality, one of the most difficult aspects of supply chain management is integrating trading partners (Frohlich, 2002; Taylor, 2003). Since several supply chain software systems are sold by a number of vendors and are developed using a variety of technologies, failing to incorporate system integration across the supply chain has become one of the key teething problems in supply chain management (Philip & Booth, 2001). The degree to which a company uses cutting-edge technology is referred to as information technology advancement (Taylor, 2003). It assesses the degree to which advanced information technology is being used to find solutions for customers ahead of the competition. Firms are gradually allocating more resources to their supply chain management structure and information technology departments in order to improve the internal skills needed to fully leverage cutting-edge technologies (Booth & Philip, 1998). The higher degree of information technology spending, on the other hand, does not always mean better use of company's capital. Significant investments in ICT do not always result in the expected benefits for a business (Barney et al., 2001; Taylor, 2003; Brynjolfsson, 1993). However, it is possible that businesses will use advanced information technology to increase the productivity of their business practices and processes (Mukhopadhyay et al., 1997; Stank et al., 1999). Perhaps in order for information technology to become a firm-specific resource and, as a result, improve its appropriability, it must be incorporated into an operational process or implemented ahead of rivals (Barney, 1991; Powell & Dent-Micallef, 1997; Tippins & Sohi, 2003). Implementing advanced information technology ahead of rivals, increases the chances that the company will succeed. Owner-operated companies reap a range of advantages. When accumulated, a high level of information technology innovation is likely to have additional advantages not available to late adopters. Nonetheless, information technology innovation represents a company's competitive focus on embracing cutting-edge technology in order to remain ahead of the competition. Information technology becomes uncommon and ineptly mobile in such an environment of firms, and it can offer exclusive advantages to implementing firms by higher productivity than its competitors for at least a certain span of years (Collis, 1994; Philip & Booth, 2001). In view of the above literature, the study hypothesized that:

H2: Information Technology has a positive effect on effective supply chain management

2.2.3 Mediating role of information technology infrastructure between supply chain management and firm performance

In many ways, the advancement of information technology in supply chain management structures will aid in the development of stronger supply chain capabilities. First, advanced supply chain management structure equipment has the ability to improve the speed, efficiency, and volume of data transmitted (Garay-Rondero et al., 2019; Gandi et al., 2017; Booth & Philip, 1998; Malone et al., 1987; Clemons & Row, 1993) information technology will guarantee the timeliness and availability of appropriate and essential information to - party concerned by speeding up the collection and sharing of information (Tippins & Sohi, 2003). Second, integrating cutting-edge information technology in the supply chain system can improve collaboration and lower business costs among associates (Clemons & Row, 1993). For example, Dell's supply chain method is well-known for its ability to efficiently organize multiple groups in the just-in-time assembly of customized system orders. As a result, Dell has a cost advantage over its competitors in the long run (Taylor, 2004). Third, a sophisticated supply chain communication system would improve the interfirm integration of channel partners (Bowersox et al., 1999). Web-based technology now allows for supply chain integration both downstream and upstream in areas including demand forecasting, inventory preparation, and order scheduling, according to Frohlich (2002).

The challenge of managing demand and supply across the complete supply chain system can be made simpler with an automated flow of knowledge between consumers and suppliers. Fourth, a successful supply chain management helps partners to react more swiftly to market shifts and consumer demands, as well as effectively share information and organize activities (Rogers et al., 1993; Stank et al., 1999 Gandi et al., 2017; Garay-Rondero et al., 2019). Investing in advanced information technology allows for greater device compatibility and performance of network associates' collaboration (Philip & Booth, 2001). Supply chain management evolution from exclusive EDI to Internet-based EDI, for example, has been widely documented across industries for businesses seeking improved device compatibility. The newly developed XML technology helps channel partners to connect and integrate much more effectively (Xml.org, 2002; Bowersox et al., 1999). Furthermore, the need for information technology alignment necessitates the sharing of costs and obligations in the implementation of new technologies by supply chain partners (Bowersox et al., 1999; Taylor, 2003 Gandi et al., 2017; Garay-Rondero et al., 2019). The pressures imposed by the entire supply chain network, as well as the potential synergistic benefits of an integrated system, will act as a catalyst for the implementation of advanced technologies to increase information technology alignment for those stakeholders who have yet to introduce a new system. As a result, a higher level of information technology innovation is thought to help in the development of greater information technology integration across the supply chain. Information technology alignment necessitates the creation of a higher level of tacit and complex integrative competence (Powell, 1992; Gandi et al., 2017; Garay-Rondero et al., 2019).

Firms can establish a greater degree of supply chain management competence by aligning various business procedures in the supply chain network, which is otherwise difficult to do while working alone. This form of capability necessitates resource integration in the supply chain procedure, and information technology alignment serves as the foundation for such integration. A company can combine products and services through an integrated supply chain structure and complementary capital into a synergistic kit that will boost both partners' rents (Amit & Schoemaker, 1993; Day, 1994 Gandi et al., 2017; Garay-Rondero et al., 2019). Improvements in information technology coordination will improve the movement of effective resource and information exchange within and through businesses in today's information-intensive world (Kearns & Lederer, 2003). It helps supply chain participants to classify valuable business information into concrete tactics in a collaborative effort. It also aids the business's strategic planning practise, which is essential in the company. To achieve organizational efficiency, firms must coordinate and distribute resources (Segars et al., 1998).

Furthermore, the difficult phase of information technology alignment is likely to increase supply chain responsiveness and cooperation with stakeholders in order to meet evolving consumer demands (Malone et al., 1987; Philip & Booth, 2001). Enhancing supply chain management can have a number of effects on firm

performance in the context of this analysis. First, information flows enabled by communication systems have the ability to increase sales volume by getting consumers directly and punctually once a new product is introduced, as well as by increasing into markets previously inaccessible due to delivery or other infrastructure limitations (Wu et al., 2003). Second, the synergistic advantages that an integrated framework provides enable a company to better react to customer complaints and demands (Rogers et al., 1993; Gandhi et al., 2017; Garay-Rondero et al., 2019). For instance, a supply chain management structure helps a business to react to customer requests, monitor customer orders, and then offer improved after-sale support through its application with a customer relationship management system (Bowersox et al., 1999). Supply chain management skills can also help a company's bottom line by giving it a cost advantage over rivals. Information sharing in the supply chain can reduce market fluctuations and inventory costs throughout the phase of matching supply with demand in the supply chain network (Frohlich, 2002). As a result, it can be concluded that improving supply chain capabilities through information technology infrastructure alignment and advancement can have a direct effect on a company's business and financial performance. In view of that, the study posits that:

H3: Information technology mediates the relationship between supply chain management and Firm performance

3. Research methodology

For the current study, the population comprised SME manufacturing firms in Rwanda. The research design used simple random and stratified sampling methods as a representative sample of SMEs in Rwanda. The sample size of the study was 300 respondents. In pursuit of data collection for the study, both supplier and buyer relationships were incorporated. However, the participants were logistics managers, procurement or purchasing officers/managers, or supply chain managers who considered the field interviews' appropriate participants. More importantly, various trade associations and unions were consulted to recruit members in the supply chain fraternity. On the contrary, freight-forward agents, consultants, and other 3rd party logistics firms were excluded. Within the three weeks, 264 questionnaires out of 300 were obtained from the two submissions, representing an 88% per cent successful response rate. The response rate comprises managers from the following SME manufacturing firms:

Table 1 Participant response rate

Firms	Response rate
Industrial Machinery	14.8%
Consumer Products	31.4%
Automotive	9.1%
Computer And Communication	13.1%
Medical Equipment	5.5%
Electronic Equipment	10.2%
Chemical	3.9%
Not Reported	12%
Total	100%

In essence, two reliable criteria were used in selecting the participants in this study following the Li and Calantone (1998). The first criteria are adapted from Seidler (1974); the participants were to take a broad view "about patterns of behaviour regarded as relevant" after briefing either expected or observed organizational associations. Given that all of our participants are business executives in charge of supply chain activities (e.g., logistics and supply chain management), it is fair to assume that they can provide a comprehensive overview of supply chain operations. Second, did the participants have any previous knowledge of the subject of the investigation? In support of Kumar et al. (1993), the participants were asked to offer a self-assessment of their proficiency in the study's topics. However, a seven-point Likert scale was used where seven (7) equal to best qualified. On the other hand, the participants' mean was 5.41, implying a reasonable qualification status for the study.

In terms of scale development, we followed Churchill's (1979) recommendations. Firstly, each construct's domain was explicitly defined based on what would be incorporated and excluded. Secondly, the evidence was combed for any scales that might be appropriate. Where applicable, measures were adapted or

adopted from the published literature. New interventions were developed if none were available or necessary. Except for firm size, all items were rated on a seven-point Likert scale, with 7 indicating "strongly agree", and 1 indicating "strongly disagree". The IT advancement scales were adapted from Gatignon and Xuereb (1997) scales for measuring technological orientation. The study adjusted the scales to show how far IT has progressed within a business. Bowersox et al. (1999) developed activity integration scales to assess the degree of interfirm cooperation. This study required the development of scales for information exchange, IT alignment, and partner coordination (Wu et al., 2006). McGinnis and Kohn (1993) constructs were used to develop supply chain adaptation, with changes made from the firm to the supply chain level. However, other scales adapted from Venkatraman and Ramanujam (1986) and Wu et al. (2006) for market performance included market share, sales growth, product development, and market development. Return on investment, profitability, and cash flow from operations were used to evaluate firms' financial performance. Finally, the business size was calculated using the participants' recorded revenue and employee count for each firm (Wu et al., 2006). To account for nonlinear effects and mitigate univariate non-normalities, the firm size variable was converted using the natural log (Wooldridge, 2000). (See Table 2 for variables' measurements).

Table 2 Variables' measurements

Construct	Item	Measurement
Supply Chain Management Information exchange	SCM1	Our business exchanges enough information with our partners compared to our competitors with our partners
	SCM2	between our business and our partners, information flows more freely than they do with our competitors
	SCM3	we benefits from information exchange with our partners more than our competitors do
	SCM4	we consider our information exchange superior with our partners than our competitors do with them
Cordination	SCM5	in terms of coordination, we are more efficient with our partners than our competitors do
	SCM6	we are more efficient in conducting transaction follow up activities with our partners than our competitors
	SCM7	we spend less time in coordinating transactions and activities with our partners than our competitors to with them
	SCM8	we reduce transaction costs in terms of coordination more than our competitors
	SCM9	we conduct coordination at less cost than our competitors
Activity integration	SCM10	we develop strategic plans in consultation with our partners
	SCM11	we collaborate actively with our partners in terms of forecasting and planning
	SCM12	our plans and projects demand future collaboration with our partners which we always focus on
	SCM13	our business always plans and forecasts activities in collaboration with our partners
Responsiveness		

	SCM 14	our supply chain is responsive more effectively and quickly as compared to our competitors to changing suppliers and customers needs
	SCM15	our supply chain is responsive more effectively and quickly as compared to our competitors' changing strategies
	SCM16	our supply chain effectively and quickly markets and develops new products as compared to our competitors
	SCM17	our supply chain is competitive in an effective way in most markets
	SCM18	our partners' relationship with us have increased our supply chain responsiveness through collaboration to market changes
Firm Performance		
	FP1	our business performs highly better in profitability than our competitors
	FP2	our business performs highly better in returns on investment than our competitors
	FP3	our business performs highly better in cash flows in operational activities than our competitors
Information Technology Infrastructure Information technology advancement		
	ITA1	our business adopts modern and advanced information technology of supply chain management
	ITA2	our information technology is a state-of-art
	ITA3	our supply management communication system surpasses our competitors
	ITA4	our business recognises IT as a top most priority
	ITA5	our business first used new IT for supply chain communication system in the industry
Information technology alignment		
	ITAL1	our technology is aligned with our partners
	ITAL2	we invest enough in IT to align with our partners
	ITAL3	our working partners invest in IT in alignment with ours
	ITAL4	we work together with our partners for the best of IT alignment
	ITAL5	between our business and our partners, our IT advances for supply chain communication system are well aligned for best performance
Firm Size		
	FS1	logarithm of sales reported by participants
	FS2	logarithm of employees reported by participants
Marketing Performance		
	MP1	our business performs highly better in sales growth than our competitors
	MP2	our business performs highly better in market share than our competitors
	MP3	our business performs highly better in market development than our competitors

MP4

our business performs highly better in product development than our competitors

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1 Findings

4.1.1 Descriptive Statistics and Correlations

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics and correlation values of the constructs. From the table, it can be observed that all the constructs are positively correlated where firm size showed the highest correlation construct to supply chain management and marketing performance also showed the highest correlation with firm performance. On the other hand, the mean and standard deviation of the constructs can be reported as supply chain management (M = 4.185, SD = 0.812), IT infrastructure advancement (M = 3.425, SD = 1.254), IT infrastructure alignment (M = 3.512, SD = 1.145), marketing performance (M = 4.756, SD = 1.112), firm performance (M = 4.956, SD = 1.362), and firm size (M = 6.523, SD = 2.231).

Table 3 Descriptive Statistics and Correlations

	Mean	SD	Correlations				
			1	2	3	4	5
1 Supply chain management	4.185	0.812	1				
2 IT infrastructure advancement	3.425	1.254	0.623	1			
3 IT infrastructure alignment	3.512	1.145	0.236	0.215	1		
4 Marketing Performance	4.756	1.112	0.425	0.415	0.125	1	
5 Firm Performance	4.956	1.362	0.326	0.321	0.152	0.856	1
6 Firm size	6.523	2.231	0.215	0.521	0.023	0.236	0.415

4.1.2 Data adequacy and Normality test

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sampling adequacy test, as well as Bartlett's test of sphericity, are used to determine if the data for the various constructs and their respective measures used in this analysis are appropriate for structure reduction. The KMO test, in particular, is a statistic that indicates the proportion of variance that could be explained by underlying factors. Table 4 shows that the KMO has a test value of 0.734 for supply chain management, 0.947 for information technology infrastructure as a mediating variable, and 0.714 for marketing efficiency, while the answer construct has a test value of 0.814. In addition, the control variable of firm size had a value of 0.763. The corresponding KMO test values for the different constructs are very high (closer to 1), indicating that the constructs under consideration have clarified a significant proportion of variance of about 73.4 percent, 94.7 percent, 78.3 percent, 81.4 percent, and 76.3 percent, respectively.

Furthermore, the results of the KMO test show that the sample data for the different constructs is sufficient for exploratory factor analysis. The hypothesis that the correlation matrix is an identity matrix is also tested by Bartlett's test of sphericity. This indicates that the variables within a construct are unrelated, making the construct unsuitable for structure detection. For the aforementioned constructs, Bartlett's test of sphericity from Table 4 yields p-values less than the degree of significance, indicating rejection of the hypothesis. As a result, the variables in the correlation matrix are connected and thus appropriate for structure reduction (factor analysis). In a summary, these tests (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test) demonstrate that the data for each of the study's constructs is sufficient for structure reduction or factor analysis. The results of the KMO and Bartlett's tests are shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Data adequacy and Normality test

Variables	No of items	KMO test value	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Kolmogorov-Smirnova	Prob.	Shapiro-Wilk	Prob.
Supply Chain management	18	0.734	476.180(0.000)***	0.334***	0.000	0.681***	0.000
Information Technology infrastructure	10	0.947	452.121(0.000)***	0.432***	0.000	0.691***	0.004
Firms' performance	3	0.814	428.079 (0.000)***	0.372***	0.025	0.784***	0.000
Marketing performance	4	0.741	391.833(0.000)***	0.327***	0.000	0.778***	0.000
Firms size	2	0.763	425.025(0.000)***	0.362***	0.001	0.632***	0.001

Table 4 shows the results of the normality test for all of the constructs used in the analysis, as revealed by the EFA method, in terms of their respective number of measurement elements. The normality test is used to assess how the data is distributed through the variables being studied. It is important to remember that the type of analytical technique or procedure used to analyze data is determined by the data distribution. The researcher must use a non-parametric test when the data is biased positively or negatively, whereas normally distributed data (Gaussian distribution) involves parametric test analysis. According to Stebbins (2001), the evaluation conditions are to obtain Shapiro Wilks and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test values greater than 0.5. Table 4 indicates that all of the parameters have a p-value greater than 0.5, indicating that the data for the different constructs were normally distributed, justifying the use of a parametric test method for the entire study.

4.1.3 Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Each construct's convergent and discriminant validity were investigated using a second-order confirmatory factor analysis (Bentler, 1989). The elliptical reweighted least squares (ERLS) procedure of the EQS framework was used to suit the measurement model that included all constructs (Bentler, 1989). Tables 5 demonstrate the findings of the study. The model is extremely well-fitting ($\chi^2 = 1076.96$ with $df = 249$, CFI = 0.917, RMSEA = 0.062, NFI = 0.913, NNFI = 0.956) because of the second-order confirmatory factor analysis's complexity. All of the items were statistically relevant and loaded on their respective constructs. Furthermore, the composite reliability and cronbach alpha for all constructs were greater than 0.7, suggesting adequate reliability, as indicated by Nunnally (1978) (see Table 4.3).

Significant factor loadings on each build were examined for convergent validity. When items weight significantly on their assigned latent variables, convergent validity is suggested, according to Anderson (1987). The convergent validity is shown by the standardized CFA loadings in Table 5. The four first-order factors have positive and statistically significant loadings on supply chain management, suggesting convergent validity at the second-order factor stage. The study used Bagozzi et al. (1991) suggested procedure to determine the discriminant validity of each construct. This involves using EQS to analyze all possible construct pairs in a sequence of two-factor confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) models (Bentler, 1989). Each model was run two times, one with the connection between constructs constrained to unity and one with the parameter unconstrained.

Table 5 Exploratory Factor Analysis

Construct	Item	Std. Loading	T-value	CR	CA
Supply Chain Management					
Information exchange				0.95	0.91
	SCM1	0.823	-		
	SCM2	0.856	13.871		
	SCM3	0.923	14.686		
	SCM4	0.906	14.723		

Cordination				0.89	0.82
	SCM5	0.827	-		
	SCM6	0.878	13.003		
	SCM7	0.712	11.641		
	SCM8	0.824	12.452		
	SCM9	0.847	13.253		
Activity integration				0.92	0.90
	SCM10	0.658	-		
	SCM11	0.725	8.958		
	SCM12	0.835	9.254		
	SCM13	0.937	12.423		
Responsiveness				0.88	0.79
	SCM 14	0.862	-		
	SCM15	0.824	13.455		
	SCM16	0.702	10.362		
	SCM17	0.746	12.652		
	SCM18	0.633	8.527		
Firm Performance				0.92	0.89
	FP1	0.956	-		
	FP2	0.926	19.236		
	FP3	0.891	13.501		
Information Technology Infrastructure					
Information technology advancement				0.89	0.82
	ITA1	0.825	-		
	ITA2	0.813	12.623		
	ITA3	0.712	9.012		
	ITA4	0.785	12.523		
	ITA5	0.829	12.963		
Information technology alignment				0.91	0.86
	ITAL1	0.817	-		
	ITAL2	0.873	12.365		
	ITAL3	0.775	10.254		
	ITAL4	0.847	16.102		
	ITAL5	0.907	15.548		
Firm Size				0.76	0.72
	FS1	0.964	-		
	FS2	0.664	2.365		
Marketing Performance				0.92	0.89
	MP1	0.832	-		
	MP2	0.871	11.542		
	MP3	0.867	12.110		
	MP4	0.789	10.086		

Subsequently, the nested models were then subjected to a chi-square (χ^2) difference test to see if the unconstrained models' χ^2 values were substantially lower. In all pairs, the critical value ($\Delta\chi^2(1) > 3.84$) was exceeded. The results show that at the one percent level, the unconstrained models' chi square values are significantly lower, meaning that the constructs have discriminant validity. Four dimensional steps with a second-order structure are hypothesized for supply chain management. Coordination, knowledge sharing, responsiveness, and task integration are the four dimensions.

To further assess the validity of supply chain management as a second-order construct, the analysis compared the model fit of a second-order model by pulling the four constructs together with another model in which the four constructs were treated as first-order constructs only. The four constructs in the second-order model suggested an appropriate model fit for the proposed structure ($\chi^2 = 349.254$ with 156 *df*, NNFI = 0.924, CFI = 0.923, RMSEA = 0.081, NFI = 0.936). Because of the second-order factor's simplicity and the slight discrepancy in fit indices between the two measurement types, the second-order factor structure is chosen for supply chain management (Hull et al., 1991).

Table 4. 1 Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Model Fitness Statistics	2ND	1ST
χ^2	1076.96	349.254
Degree of Freedom	249	156
Bentler-Bonett non normed fit index (NNFI)	0.956	0.924
Bentler-Bonett normed fit index (NFI)	0.913	0.936
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.917	0.923
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	0.062	0.081

4.1.4 Partial Least square analysis results

A complete model specification was used to assess the effect of supply chain management, IT alignment, and IT advancement on firm performance. Figure 2 shows the relationships between the variables in the complete model and their standard deviations. The overall fit statistics show that the model ($\chi^2 = 1076.96$ with *df* = 249, CFI = 0.917, RMSEA = 0.062, NFI = 0.913, NNFI = 0.956) suits the findings very well. In the hypothesized relationship, however, IT advancement has a significant positive effect on both IT coordination ($t = 0.321$, $p < 0.05$) and supply chain management ($t = 0.612$, $p < 0.05$). Thus, hypothesis 2 is supported in this findings which implies that information technology infrastructure positively relates to supply chain management as it is evidential that both IT alignment and advancement showed positive and significant relationship with supply chain management.

The total effect was assessed considering supply chain management with the mediating effect of IT alignment ($t = 0.321$, $p < 0.05$), and IT advancement ($t = 0.612$, $p < 0.05$) as well as firm performance ($t = 0.512$, $p < 0.05$) indicating that H1 and H3 are supported which implies that supply chain management positively relates to IT infrastructure which positively influence firms' performance significantly. More to it, the size of a firm and its marketing performance do matter regarding the relationship among supply chain management, information technology infrastructure and firm's performance even though they positively influence such linkage but it is somewhat insignificant.

Figure 2 Full model estimates

4.2 Discussion

4.2.1 Supply chain management, information technology (IT), and firms' performance

While supply chain management is critical in understanding the impact of IT on business success, achieving these goals is difficult. Supply chain management, as a higher-order organizational skill, illustrates a company's ability to coordinate resources effectively using information-based organizational processes to serve customers (Amit & Schoemaker, 1993; Gandhi et al., 2017; Garay-Rondero et al., 2019). In order to complete the tasks efficiently and effectively, the supply chain needs a higher level of information integration from different viewpoints and multiple stakeholders (Grant, 1996). The results indicate that IT innovation and coordination will help supply chain management to grow more quickly. Organisations are expected to achieve higher efficiency in channel activities than their rivals, both within the organization and with stakeholders, by deploying the latest technology for supply chain management structure, particularly before it is widely circulated (Boone & Ganeshan, 2001; Philip & Booth, 2001; Porter, 2001; Gandhi et al., 2017; Garay-Rondero et al., 2019). Supply chain management structure will benefit from advanced IT by improving knowledge sharing and communication between partner companies (Sahin & Robinson, 2002).

The world has become smaller as a result of the interconnectedness brought on by information technology. Previously independent decision-making processes from upstream producers to downstream consumers are being closely interconnected (Bowersox et al., 1999; Gandhi et al., 2017). In fact, the purpose of information sharing, according to Vakharia (2002), is to "promote structured and/or systematic decision making in the supply chain." Effective supply chain communication can also help companies reduce inventory costs, forecast consumer demand, and respond more quickly to customer requests (Lin et al., 2002). Owing to high prices, delivery delays, and the potential loss of confidential information, supply chain partners are also opposed to changes in the process of e-integration into the supply chain (Frohlich, 2002). Technological incompatibility is one of the most common causes of supply chain disruption (Taylor, 2003). The results indicate that aligning information technology with partner companies is just as essential, if not more significant, in improving a company's competitive advantage via supply chain communication networks.

The value of strategic alignment between IT and a company's overall business strategy has been studied in the past (Kearns & Lederer, 2003). The new study looks at how IT alignment affects the global supply chain. It also contains some useful supply chain management advice. We discovered that channel partners must strive for technology functionality across the supply chain, not just in the supply chain management system (Hausman & Stock, 2003). In order to realize the full potential of their IT commitment, all partners must invest in IT at the same time. However, since the supply chain system often employs a variety of emerging technology and necessitates a high level of financial involvement from all network stakeholders,

IT alignment poses both challenges and opportunities for effective supply chain management (Garay-Rondero et al., 2019; Hausman & Stock, 2003; Gandi et al., 2017).

4.2.2 The mediating role of information technology in the relationship between supply chain management and firms' performance

This study looked into the role of IT investment as a key mediator between supply chain management and firm efficiency. The findings show that supply chain management will increase the value of IT-related resources for a business (Wu et al., 2006). By incorporating IT into a company's supply chain structure, it will enhance channel-specific assets by promoting information sharing and enhancing coordination with supply chain partners. A higher level of supply chain capabilities gives the business a knowledge advantage over competitors since it allows it to access and even incorporate data from multiple sources that would otherwise be unavailable if it operated alone. Information technology has strengthened the firm's supply chain management, helping it to learn and react to market changes better and faster than rivals. Furthermore, since these abilities are developed over time and are deeply embedded in organizational routines, a company with them would be protected from rapid competitive imitation. This is the foundation for a sustainable competitive advantage (Barney, 1991; Bharadwaj, 2000).

Because of the mediation impact of information technology, including appropriate mediators may be able to help clarify the effects of supply chain management on firm results. The current study offers some explanations for the inconsistencies in IT's effects on firm productivity (Brynjolfsson, 1993; Wu et al., 2006; Gandi et al., 2017; Garay-Rondero et al., 2019). Brynjolfsson (Brynjolfsson, 1993). Analyzing the impact of IT in a specific context, such as a company's supply chain system, will help better gauge the impact of IT on firm performance, according to the findings (Barney et al., 2001).

The results have implications for supply chain management as well. In order to recognize the value of information technology assets, managers must consider the importance of supply chain skills. According to the resource-based perspective, information technology capabilities have benefits when they are integrated into a specific organizational strategy (Barney, 1991). The study explores the mediating impact of IT resources on firm performance in the sense of supply chain management (Gandi et al., 2017; Garay-Rondero et al., 2019). According to the findings, a proper information technology resource deployment in supply chain management will aid in realizing the benefits of information technology by improving supply chain capabilities in capacities like knowledge sharing, collaboration, operation integration, and supply chain sensitivity. The research also backs up the idea of supply chain capacity as a higher-order framework (Garay-Rondero et al., 2019). Managers must be able to connect the dots between the various aspects of supply chain management. Investment in the supply chain framework, which must be organized through all partner companies in order to realize the full potential of information technology, must be organized through all partner companies in order to realize the full potential of information technology (Wu et al., 2006). Moreover, supply chain management based on well-balanced supply chain activities is more likely to contribute to firm success than supply chain management based on imbalanced and fragmented activities.

According to the research, a successful information technology implementation requires not only modern, cutting-edge technology, but also the recognition of the context in which information technology will be used. That is, management must assess the appropriate perspective for distributing information technology resources and reorganize strategy implementation so that information technology can achieve its maximum potential (Swanson, 1994; Gandi et al., 2017). Executives in the supply chain must recognize that information technology alignment is a critical component of effective information technology implementation. The returns from information technology would be maximized only when management are able to effectively and efficiently organize information technology investments in supply chain networks through channel partners (Wu et al., 2006).

5. Conclusion

This study's major objective is to evaluate the mediating role of information technology on the relationship between supply chain management and firm performance in Rwanda. The research design used simple random and stratified sampling methods as a representative sample of SMEs in Rwanda. The sample size of

the study was 300 respondents. In pursuit of data collection for the study, both supplier and buyer relationships were incorporated. However, the participants were logistics managers, procurement or purchasing officers/managers, or supply chain managers who considered the field interviews' appropriate participants. More importantly, various trade associations and unions were consulted to recruit members in the supply chain fraternity. On the contrary, freight-forward agents, consultants, and other 3rd party logistics firms were excluded. The data was analyzed using appropriate models for appropriateness, convenience, clarity, and simplicity. The models such as structural equation modelling was used to evaluate the direct and indirect effect of information technology on supply chain management in Rwanda. However, the elliptical reweighted least squares (ERLS) procedure of the EQS program was used as the statistical tools to analyze the research.

The overall fit statistics show that the model suits the results very well in its entirety ($\chi^2 = 1076.96$ with $df = 249$, $CFI = 0.917$, $RMSEA = 0.062$, $NFI = 0.913$, $NNFI = 0.956$). However, IT advancement has a substantial positive impact on both IT alignment ($t = 0.321$, $p < 0.05$) and supply chain management ($t = 0.612$, $p < 0.05$) in the hypothesized relationship. Thus, hypothesis 2 is supported in this findings which implies that information technology infrastructure positively relates to supply chain management as it is evidential that both information technology alignment and advancement showed positive and significant relationship with supply chain management. The total effect was assessed considering supply chain management with the mediating effect of information technology alignment ($t = 0.321$, $p < 0.05$), and information technology advancement ($t = 0.612$, $p < 0.05$) as well as firm performance ($t = 0.512$, $p < 0.05$) indicating that H1 and H3 are supported which implies that supply chain management positively relates to information technology infrastructure which positively influence firms' performance significantly.

References

- i. Achrol, R. S., & Etzel, M. J. (2003). *The Structure of Reseller Goals and Performance in Marketing Channels*. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 31(2), 146-163.
- ii. Akkermans, H.A., Bogerd, P., Yucensan, E., & Wassenhove, L.N. (2003). *The impact of ERP on supply chain management: Exploratory findings from a European Delphi Study*. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 146, 284-301.
- iii. Amit, R., & Schoemaker, P. J. H. (1993). *Strategic assets and organizational rent*. *Strategic Management Journal*, 14(1), 33– 46.
- iv. Auramo, J., Kauremaa, J., & Tanskanen, K. (2005). *Benefits of IT in supply chain management: An explorative study of progressive companies*. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*. 35, 82-100
- v. Bagorogoza, J., & Waal, A. D. (2010). *The Role of Knowledge Management in Creating and Sustaining High Performance Organizations the Case of Financial Institutions in Uganda*. *World Journal of Entrepreneurship Management and Sustainable Development*, 6(4), 307-323.
- vi. Bakar, L. J., & Ahmad, H. (2010). *Assessing the Relationship between Firm Resources and Product Innovation Performance*. *Business Process Management Journal*, 16(3), 420-435.
- vii. Barney, J. (1991). *Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage*. *Journal of Management*, 17(1), 99–120.
- viii. Barney, J., Wright, M., & Ketchen Jr., D. J. (2001). *The resource-based view of the firm: Ten years after 1991*. *Journal of Management*, 27(6), 625–641.
- ix. Bensaou, M. (1997). *Interorganizational Cooperation: The Role of Information Technology an Empirical Comparison of U.S. and Japan Supplier Relations*. *Information Systems Research*, 8(2), 107-123.
- x. Bentler, P. M. (1989). *EQS Structural Equations Program manual*. Encino, CA' Multivariate Software Inc.
- xi. Bharadwaj, A. S. (2000). *A resource-based perspective on information technology capability and firm performance: An empirical investigation*. *MIS Quarterly*, 24(1), 169–196.
- xii. Boddy, D., Macbeth, D. & Wagner, B. (2000). *Implementing collaboration between organizations: an empirical study of supply chain partnering*. *Journal of Management Studies*, 37(7), 1003-1018.

- xiii. Boone, T., & Ganeshan, R. (2001). *The effect of information technology on learning in professional service organizations*. *Journal of Operations Management*, 19(4), 485– 495.
- xiv. Booth, M. E., & Philip, G. (1998). *Technology, competencies, and competitiveness: The case for reconfigurable and flexible strategies*. *Journal of Business Research*, 41(1), 29– 40.
- xv. Bowersox, D.J., Closs, D.J., Stank, T.P., (1999). *21st century logistics: Making supply chain integration a reality*. East Lansing: Michigan State University and Council of Logistics Management.
- xvi. Bryman, A., & Bell, E. (2015). *Business research methods*. Oxford University Press, USA.
- xvii. Brynjolfsson, E. (1993). *The productivity paradox of information technology*. *Communications of the ACM*, 36(12), 67– 77.
- xviii. Castelli, C.M. & Brun, A. (2010). *Alignment of retail channels in the fashion supply chain an empirical study of Italian fashion retailers*. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 38(1), 24-44.
- xix. Clark, T. H., & Stoddard, D. B. (1996). *Interorganizational business process redesign: Merging technological and process innovation*. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 13(2), 9 – 28.
- xx. Clemons, E. K., & Row, M. C. (1991). *Sustaining IT advantage: The role of structural differences*. *MIS Quarterly*, 15(3), 275– 292.
- xxi. Clemons, E. K., & Row, M. C. (1993). *Limits to interfirm coordination through information technology: Results of a field study in consumer packaged goods distribution*. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 10(1), 73– 95.
- xxii. Collis, D. J. (1994). *Research note: How valuable are organizational capabilities?* *Strategic Management Journal*, 15, 143– 152
- xxiii. Cooper, M.C., Lamberth, D.M., & Pagh, J.D. (1997). *Supply chain management: more than a new name for logistics*. *The International Journal of Logistics Management*, 8(1), 1-14.
- xxiv. Christopher, M., & Peck, H. (2007). *'Building the Resilient Supply Chain*. Retrieved from <http://www.martinchristopher.info/downloads/building%20the%20resilient%20supply%20chain.pdf>
- xxv. Day, G. S. (1994). *The capabilities of market-driven organizations*. *Journal of Marketing*, 58(4), 37–52.
- xxvi. Day, M. & Lichtenstein, S. (2006). *Strategic supply management: the relationship between supply management practices, strategic orientation and their impact on organisational performance*. *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, 12(6), 313-321.
- xxvii. De Toni, A. & Nassimbeni, G. (2000). *Just-in-time purchasing: an empirical study of operational practices, supplier development and performance*. *Omega: The International Journal of Management Science*, 28(6), 31-651.
- xxviii. Dobbs, M., & Hamilton, R.T. (2006). *Small Business Growth: Recent Evidence and New Directions*. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research*, 13 (5), 296-322.
- xxix. Frohlich, M. T. (2002). *E-integration in the supply chain: Barriers and performance*. *Decision Sciences*, 33(4), 537– 556.
- xxx. Gandhi, A.V., Shaikh, A., & Sheorey, P. A. (2017). *Impact of supply chain management practices on firm performance: Empirical evidence from a developing country*. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 45(4), 366-384, <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJRDM-06-2015-0076>
- xxxi. Garay-Rondero, Z.L., Martinez-Flores, L.J., Smith, R.N., Morales, S.O.C., & Aldrette-Malacara, A. (2019). *Digital supply chain model in Industry 4.0*. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 1741-038X, DOI 10.1108/JMTM-08-2018-0280
- xxxii. Garrigos-Simon, F. J., & Marques, D. P. (2004). *Competitive Strategies and Firm Performance: A Study in the Spanish Hospitality Sector*. *Management Research*, 2(3), 251–269.
- xxxiii. Gatignon, H., & Xuereb, J. (1997). *Strategic orientation of the firm and new product performance*. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 34(1), 77–90.

- xxxiv. Gharakhani, D., Mavi, R.K. and Hamidi, N. (2012). *Impact of supply chain management practices on innovation and organizational performance in Iranian companies*. *African Journal of Business Management*, 6(19), 5939-5949.
- xxxv. Grant, R.M., Jammine, A.P., & Thomas, H. (1988). *Diversity, Diversification, and Profitability among British Manufacturing Companies 1972–1984*. *Academy of Management Journal*, 31, 771–801.
- xxxvi. Grant, R. M. (1996, Winter Special Issue). *Toward a knowledge-based theory of the firm*. *Strategic Management Journal*, 17, 109–122.
- xxxvii. Gravetter, F. J., & Forzano, L. A. B. (2018). *Research methods for the behavioural sciences*. Cengage Learning.
- xxxviii. Gunasekaran, A. & Chung, W.W.C. (2004). *Special issue on supply chain management for the 21st century organizational competitiveness*. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 87(3), 209-212.
- xxxix. Hausman, A., & Stock, J. R. (2003). *Adoption and implementation of technological innovations within long-term relationships*. *Journal of Business Research*, 56(8), 681– 686.
- xl. Hair, J., Ringle C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2011). *PLS-SEM: Indeed, a Silver Bullet*. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 19(2), 139–151.
- xli. Hillman, M., & Keltz, H. (2007). *Managing risk in the supply chain – A quantitative study*. Retrieved from <http://www.amrresearch.com/Content/View.aspx?pmillid=19994>
- xlii. Hult, G.T.M., Ketchen, D.J., & Slater, S.F. (2004). *Information Processing, Knowledge Development, and Strategic Supply Chain Relationship*. *Academy of Management Journal*, 47(2), 241-253.
- xliii. Hunt, S., & Morgan, R. (1995, April). *The comparative advantage theory of competition*. *Journal of Marketing*, 59, 1 – 15.
- xliv. Inkpen, A.C., & Dinur, A. (1998). *Knowledge Management Process and International Joint Ventures*. *Organization Science*, 9(4), 454-468.
- xlv. Jadhav, V.V. (2015). *Role of Information Technology in Supply Chain Management*. *International Journal of Management Research & Review*, 5(6), 369-379.
- xlvi. Kearns, G. S., & Lederer, A. L. (2003). *A resource-based view of strategic IT alignment: How knowledge sharing creates competitive advantage*. *Decision Sciences*, 34(1), 1– 19.
- xlvii. Kumar, N., Stern, L. W., & Anderson, J. G. (1993). *Conducting interorganizational research using key informants*. *Academy of Management Journal*, 36(6), 1633–1651.
- xlviii. Lambert, D. M., & Cooper, M. C. (2000). *Issues in Supply Chain Management*. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 29, 65-83.
- xlix. Lee, L. S., Fiedler, K. D., & Smith, J. S. (2008). *Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) Implementation in the Service Section: A Customer-facing Diffusion Model*. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 11(2), 587 – 600.
- l. Li, T., & Calantone, R. J. (1998). *The impact of market knowledge competence on new product advantage: Conceptualization and empirical examination*. *Journal of Marketing*, 62(4), 13– 29.
- li. Li, S., Rao, S., Ragu Nathan, T. & Ragu Nathan, B. (2005). *Development and validation of a measurement instrument for studying supply chain management practices*. *Journal of Operations Management*, 23(6), 618-641.
- lii. Lin, C. H., Peng, C. H., & Kao, D. T. (2008). *The innovativeness effect of market orientation and learning orientation on business performance*. *International Journal on Manpower*, 29(8), 725-772. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/01437720810919332>
- liii. Lin, F., Huang, S., & Lin, S. (2002). *Effects of information sharing on supply chain performance in electronic commerce*. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 49(3), 258– 268.
- liv. Lincoln, J. R., Ahmadjian, C. L., & Mason, E. (1998), *Organizational Learning and Purchase-Supply Relations in Japan: Hitachi, Matsushita, and Toyota Compared*. *California Management Review*, 40(3), 241.
- lv. MacCarthy, B.L., Blome, C., Olhager, J., Srari, J.S., & Zhao, X. (2016). *Supply chain evolution theory, concepts and science*. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 36(12), 1696-1718.

- lvi. Malhotra, A., Gosain, S., & El Sawy, O.A. (2005). *Absorptive Capacity Configurations in Supply Chains: Gearing for Partner Enabled Market Knowledge Creation*. *MIS Quarterly*, 29(1), 145-187.
- lvii. Malone, T. W., Yates, J., & Benjamin, R. I. (1987). *Electronic markets and electronic hierarchies*. *Communications of the ACM*, 30(6), 484-497.
- lviii. McGinnis, M. A., & Kohn, J. W. (1993). *Logistics strategy, organizational environment, and time competitiveness*. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 14(2), 1-23.
- lix. Min, S., Zacharia, Z.G., & Smith, C.D. (2019). *Defining supply chain management: in the past, present, and future*. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 40(1), 44-55.
- lx. Mohr, J., & Sohi, R. S. (1995). *Communication flows in distribution channels: Impact on assessments of communication quality and satisfaction*. *Journal of Retailing*, 71(4), 393-416.
- lxi. Mukhopadhyay, T., Rajiv, S., & Srinivasan, K. (1997). *Information technology impact on process output and quality*. *Management Science*, 43(12), 1645-1659.
- lxii. Narasimhan, R. & Kim, S.W. (2002). *Effect of supply chain integration on the relationship between diversification and performance: evidence from Japanese and Korean firms*. *Journal of Operations Management*, 20(3), 303-323.
- lxiii. Niu, Y. (2010). *The impact of information technology on supply chain Performance: a knowledge management perspective*. Unpublished Doctoral dissertation, A dissertation University of North Carolina, Charlotte, 1-221.
- lxiv. Oettmeier, K., & Hofmann, E. (2016). *Impact of additive manufacturing technology adoption on supply chain management processes and components*. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 27(7), 944-968.
- lxv. Oh, J., & Rhee, S. K. (2008). *The Influence of Supplier Capabilities and Technology Uncertainty on Manufacturer-Supplier Collaboration*. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 28(6), 490-517.
- lxvi. Philip, G., & Booth, M. E. (2001). *A new six 'S' framework on the relationship between the role of Information Systems (IS) and competencies in 'IS' management*. *Journal of Business Research*, 51(3), 233-247.
- lxvii. Powell, T. C. (1992). *Organizational alignment as competitive advantage*. *Strategic Management Journal*, 13(2), 119-134.
- lxviii. Powell, T. C., & Dent-Micallef, A. (1997). *Information technology as competitive advantage: The role of human business, and technology resources*. *Strategic Management Journal*, 18(5), 375-405.
- lxix. Porter, M. E. (2001). *Strategy and the internet*. *Harvard Business Review*, 79(3), 62-78.
- lxx. Rai, A., Patnayakuni, R., & Seth, N. (2006). *Firm performance impacts of digitally enabled supply chain integration capabilities*. *MIS Quarterly*, 30(2), 225-246.
- lxxi. Raut, R.D., Bhasin, H.V. & Kamble, S.S. (2012). *Analysing the effect of uncertain environmental factors on supplier-buyer strategic partnership (SBSP) by using structural equation model (SEM)*. *International Journal of Procurement Management*, 5(2), 202-228.
- lxxii. Ringle, C.M., Wende, S., & Becker, J.M. (2015). *SmartPLS 3, Hamburg: SmartPLS*. Retrieved from <http://www.smartpls.com>
- lxxiii. Raghunathan, S., & Yeh, A. (2001). *Beyond EDI: Impact of Continuous Replenishment Program (CRP) between a Manufacturer and its Retailers*. *Information Systems Research*, 12(4), 406-419.
- lxxiv. Rogers, D. S., Daugherty, P. J., & Stank, T. P. (1993). *Enhancing service responsiveness: The strategic potential of EDI*. *Logistics Information Management*, 6(3), 27-32.
- lxxv. Rosli, M. M., & Sidek, S. (2013). *The impact of innovation on the performance of small and medium manufacturing enterprises: Evidence from Malaysia*. *Journal of Innovation Management in Small & Medium Enterprises*, 1.
- lxxvi. Rubio, A., & Aragon, A. (2009). *SMEs Competitive Behavior: Strategic Resources and Strategies*. *Management Research*, 7(3), 171-190.
- lxxvii. Sahin, F., & Robinson, E. P. (2002). *Flow coordination and information sharing in supply chains: Review, implications, and directions for future research*. *Decision Sciences*, 33(4), 505-536.

- lxxviii. Seidler, J. (1974). *On using informants: A technique for collecting quantitative data and controlling for measurement error in organizational analysis*. *American Sociological Review*, 39, 816–831.
- lxxix. Scott, J.E. (2000). *Facilitating Interorganizational Learning with Information Technology*. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 17(2), 81-113.
- lxxx. Segars, A. H., Grover, V., & Teng, J. T. C. (1998). *Strategic information systems planning: Planning system dimensions, internal coalignment, and implications for planning effectiveness*. *Decision Sciences*, 29(2), 303– 345.
- lxxxi. Shah, R., Goldstein, S. M., & Ward, P.T. (2002). *Aligning Supply Chain Management Characteristics and Interorganizational Information Systems Types: An Exploratory Study*. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 49(3), 282.
- lxxxii. Sharma, R., & Kaur, D. (2017). *Role of Information Technology in Supply Chain Management*. *Biz and Bytes*, 8(1), 33-36.
- lxxxiii. Shin, N. (1999). *Does information technology improve coordination? An empirical analysis*. *Logistics Information Management*, 12(1/2), 138– 144.
- lxxxiv. Shore, B., & Venkatachalam, A. R. (2003). *Evaluating the information sharing capabilities of supply chain partners: A fuzzy logic model*. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 33(9/10), 804– 824.
- lxxxv. Sinkula, J. M., Baker, W. E., & Noordewier, T. (1997). *A framework for market-based organizational learning: Linking values, knowledge, and behavior*. *Journal of Academy of Marketing Science*, 25(4), 305– 318.
- lxxxvi. Srivastava, R. K., Fahey, L., & Christensen, H. K. (2001). *The resource based view and marketing: The role of market-based assets in gaining competitive advantage*. *Journal of Management*, 27(6), 777– 802.
- lxxxvii. Srivastava, R. K., Shervani, T. A., & Fahey, L. (1998). *Market-based assets and shareholder value: A framework for analysis*. *Journal of Marketing*, 62(1), 2– 18.
- lxxxviii. Srivastava, R. K., Shervani, T. A., & Fahey, L. (1999). *Marketing, business processes, and shareholder value: An organizationally embedded view of marketing activities and the discipline of marketing*. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 63, 168– 179.
- lxxxix. Srinivasan, K., Kekre, S., & Mukhopadhyay, T. (1994). *Impact of Electronic Data Interchange Technology on JIT Shipments*. *Management Science* 40(10),
- xc. Stank, T., Crum, M., & Arango, M. (1999). *Benefits of interfirm coordination in food industry supply chains*. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 20(2), 21–41.
- xc. Stevens, G. (1989). *Integrating the supply chain*. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Materials Management*, 19(8), 3-8, <https://doi.org/10.1108/EUM00000000000329>
- xcii. Straub, D. W., Rai, A., & Klein, R. (2004). *Measuring Firm Performance at the Network Level: A Nomology of the Business Impact of Digital Supply Networks*. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 21(1), 83–114.
- xciii. Sundram, V.P.K., Ibrahim, A.R. & Govindaraju, V.G.R.C. (2011). *Supply chain management practices in the electronics industry in Malaysia: consequences for supply chain performance. Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 18(6), 834-855.
- xciv. Tavitiyaman, P., Zhang, H. Q., & Qu, H. (2012). *The Effect of Competitive Strategies and Organizational Structure on Hotel Performance*. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 24(1), 140- 159.
- xcv. Taylor, D. A. (2003). *Supply chain vs. supply chain*. *Computerworld*, 37(45), 44– 45.
- xcvi. Teece, D. J., Pisano, G., & Shuen, A. (1997). *Dynamic capabilities and strategic management*. *Strategic Management Journal*, 18(7), 509–533.
- xcvii. Tippins, M. J., & Sohi, R. S. (2003). *IT competency and firm performance: Is organizational learning a missing link? Strategic Management Journal*, 24(8), 745– 761.
- xcviii. Tu, M., Lim, M.K., & Yang, M.F. (2018). *IoT-based production logistics and supply chain system – Part 2*. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 118(1), 96-125.
- xcix. Vakharia, A. J. (2002). *E-business and supply chain management*. *Decision Sciences*, 33(4), 495–504.

- c. *Wernerfelt, B. (1984). A resource-based view of the firm. Strategic Management Journal, 5(2), 171–180.*
- ci. *Wooldridge, J. M. (2000). Introductory econometrics: A modern approach. South-Western College Publishing*
- cii. *Wolff, J.A., & Pett, T.L. (2006). Small-firm Performance: Modeling the Role of Product and Process Improvements. Journal of Small Business Management, 44 (2), 268-84.*
- ciii. *Wu, F., Mahajan, V., & Balasubramanian, S. (2003). An analysis of ebusiness adoption and its impact on business performance. Journal of Academy of Marketing Science, 31(4), 425– 447.*
- civ. *Xml.org, (2002). XML FAQ. Available at <http://www.xml.org/xml/xmlfaq.shtml>*
- cv. *Zahra, S. A. (2008). Being Entrepreneurial and Market Driven: Implications for Company Performance. Journal of Strategy and Management, 1 (2), 125-142.*